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**MEDICAL STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE OF
BASIC LIFE SUPPORT**

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ABSTRACT:

Basic life support (BLS) is a form of medical treatment offered to people who are suffering from life-threatening illnesses or injuries before they can obtain full medical attention at a hospital. It can be provided by both skilled medical professionals and qualified civilians, such as emergency medical technicians. This survey was carried out among a variety of medical and dental students. A pre-made questionnaire was given out. They were asked basic questions about basic life support, such as what it is, if they have attended any seminars on the subject, if they have supported others in this process, and so on. SPSS Ver. 23.0 was used to analyze all the results. The study enlisted the participation of 130 medical and dental students. Many of the students were in their fourth and final years. There were 80 male and 50 females in the study. The average age was 23.12 ± 2.22 . Out of 130 students, 51 had comprehensive knowledge of basic life support, 43 had some knowledge, and the remaining had no knowledge. Out of the 51 people with extensive knowledge, 16 had assisted a senior in this procedure while on duty, and 7 had attended a workshop on the subject.

**KEYWORD: MEDICAL STUDENTS, BASIC LIFE
SUPPORT**

INTRODUCTION:

Basic life support (BLS) is a form of medical treatment offered to people who are suffering from life-threatening illnesses or injuries before they can obtain full medical attention at a hospital. It can be provided by both skilled medical professionals and qualified civilians, such as emergency medical technicians. In 1992, the International Liaison Committee on Resuscitation (ILCOR) was created to coordinate resuscitation efforts around the world. Representatives from the United States, Canada, Australia, Europe, New Zealand, and the Asian and African continents make up the ILCOR membership. The first resuscitation guidance was issued by the committee in 2000. The International Consensus on Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation (CPR) and Emergency Cardiovascular Care (ECC) Science with Treatment Recommendations was issued by the committee in 2005. Since 2010, the committee has given materials to regional resuscitation organizations such as the European Resuscitation Council and the American Heart Association in order for them to write their own guidelines. Since 2015, ILCOR has used a new approach called Consensus on Science with Treatment Guidelines (COSTR) to determine the validity of the most recent evidence and come to a decision on the appropriate resuscitation therapies. ILCOR began conducting annual assessments and releasing reports on the latest evidence in resuscitation using the COSTR approach, as opposed to the previous 5-yearly analysis. CPR in the field extends the time it takes for higher-level emergency responders to arrive and provide ALS care. The automatic external defibrillator, or AED, is a major development in providing BLS. This raises the probability of recovery in cardiac arrest situations.

In a study of medical, dental, and nursing students, physicians, and nurses in India, the awareness of BLS was found to be extremely low. Another research from South Africa found that medical practitioners lacked basic resuscitation knowledge and skills. In 2009, medical students from Karachi, Pakistan, were examined, and it was discovered that more than half of them did not know BLS; it was concluded that prior BLS training would boost

awareness and application. On the other hand, despite undergoing life support training, junior doctors in the United Kingdom were found to be incapable of performing successful resuscitation. All of these examples from diverse regions suggest that health practitioners and undergraduate students in similar fields have a limited understanding of BLS (1-3).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This survey was carried out among a variety of medical and dental students. A pre-made questionnaire was given out. They were asked basic questions about basic life support, such as what it is, if they have attended any seminars on the subject, if they have supported others in this process, and so on. SPSS Ver. 23.0 was used to analyze all the results. A statistical review was carried out. The frequency and percentages were used to present the qualitative variables. The mean and standard deviation of the quantitative variables were presented.

RESULTS:

The study enlisted the participation of 130 medical and dental students. Many of the students were in their fourth and final years. There were 80 male and 50 females in the study. The average age was 23.12 ± 2.22 . Out of 130 students, 51 had comprehensive knowledge of basic life support, 43 had some knowledge, and the remaining had no knowledge. Out of the 51 people with extensive knowledge, 16 had assisted a senior in this procedure while on duty, and 7 had attended a workshop on the subject.

DISCUSSION:

Since health care practitioners are often faced with such emergency situations, they should be well-versed in BLS. Aside from physicians and nurses, dental practitioners experience life-threatening medical emergencies as part of their job as health care providers. According to a report, about two-thirds of dentists encountered at least one emergency during the 12-month

study period. Furthermore, some studies suggest that patients died as a result of cardiopulmonary arrest while undergoing dental care. Basic life support (abbreviated BLS) is intended to save lives in a number of circumstances that need urgent assistance. Cardiac arrest, stroke, drowning, coughing, accidental injury, abuse, extreme allergic reactions, burns, hypothermia, birth complications, drug addiction, and alcohol intoxication are examples of these circumstances. Cerebral hypoxia, a lack of oxygen to the brain caused by heart or respiratory failure, is the most serious emergency that involves BLS. Without basic life support, a victim of cerebral hypoxia may die in 8–10 minutes. The lowest level of emergency care is basic life support, which is followed by advanced life support and critical care (4-6).

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